

Potential of Manuka Honey as a natural polyelectrolyte to develop biomimetic nanostructured meshes with antimicrobial properties

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20 functionalisation⁴, Soft Tissue Regeneration⁵.

21 Abstract

22 The use of antibiotics has been the cornerstone to prevent bacterial infections; however, the
23 emergency of antibiotic resistant bacteria is still an open challenge. This work aimed to develop a
24 delivery system for treating soft tissue infections for: (1) reducing the released antimicrobial amount,
25 preventing drug-related systemic side effects, (2) re-discovering the beneficial effects of naturally-
26 derived agents, and (3) preserving the substrate functional properties. For the first time Manuka
27 honey (MH) was proposed as polyelectrolyte within the layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly. Biomimetic
28 electrospun poly(ϵ -caprolactone) meshes were treated via LbL assembly to obtain a multilayered
29 nanocoating, consisting of MH as polyanion and poly-(allylamine-hydrochloride) as polycation.
30 Physico-chemical characterisation demonstrated the successful nano-coating formation. Different cell
31 lines (Human immortalized and primary skin fibroblasts, and primary endothelial cells) confirmed
32 positively the membranes cytocompatibility, while bacterial tests using Gram-negative and Gram-

33 positive bacteria demonstrated the antimicrobial MH activity was dependent on the concentration
34 used and strains tested.

35 **1 Introduction**

36 Skin and soft tissue infections (SSTIs) are the most common bacterial infections, encompassing a
37 variety of pathological conditions that involve skin and underlying subcutaneous tissue, fascia, and
38 muscles (1). In the US alone, they account for ~10% of hospital admissions, and they are the most
39 significant cause of morbidity and mortality among hospitalized patients, posing considerable
40 diagnostic and therapeutic challenges (2). Moreover, the ageing population and the higher number of
41 critically ill patients are playing a crucial role on the incidence of SSTIs, which have increased
42 meaningfully over the past two decades (3). The antibiotics has been the cornerstone to prevent
43 bacterial infections. However, several drawbacks, associated with their adoption, have posed serious
44 issues towards their efficacy: i) bacterial resistance following the release of each new drug, ii) lack of
45 wide spectrum action, and iii) reduced function because of the biofilm layers formed by some
46 bacteria (4, 5). For minimizing SSTIs consequences, including the huge financial burden they cause
47 onto the healthcare services and the significant societal costs (6), the development of novel and more
48 effective antimicrobial strategies has revealed of paramount importance. Many studies report the
49 importance to inhibit the growth of bacteria in the early biofilm formation stage, thus preventing the
50 infection from starting (7). In this regards, the use of technologies at the nanoscale, to develop
51 antibacterial surfaces and coatings, has received great attention within the scientific community, as
52 promising frontier to reduce SSTIs (8).

53 Among the nanotechnologies Layer-by-layer (LbL) electrostatic assembly provides to develop
54 multilayered nano-coatings, based on the alternating exposure of a charged substrate to solutions of
55 positively and negatively charged polyelectrolytes (PEs), where a rinsing step is generally included in
56 order to prevent cross-contamination of the PE solutions. LbL method is an inexpensive and
57 environmentally-friendly, versatile and simple technique that allows to achieve desired properties and
58 fine control of the coating thicknesses by adjusting the deposition cycle conditions (9). Furthermore,
59 being electrostatic interaction the driving force of LbL assembly, almost any type of charged specie
60 (eg. organic molecules or biological macromolecules) can be incorporated into any LbL-treated
61 surfaces (eg. sheets, fibers, etc) (10, 11). Within this study, the authors demonstrated that the main
62 advantage of LbL assembly was the relatively small amount of loaded biomolecules/drugs needed to
63 achieve effective concentrations. This has been reported in previous works, where meshes were
64 functionalised with LbL assembly in order to impart a cascade of nano-stimuli and to control the
65 adhesion, proliferation and differentiation of stem cells with the consequent formation of new bone
66 matrix (12) as well as to effectively deliver the metronidazole drug from oral implant (13).

67 Numerous antibiotic-based coatings, constructed via the LbL assembly technique and intended for
68 the development of antibacterial implants, have been investigated so far, given the long-acting
69 stability of LbL film surfaces in comparison to other functionalisation techniques (14, 15). However,
70 it has been found that the effect of antibiotics may decrease with time, since antibiotic resistant
71 bacteria may potentially develop (16). Therefore, the emergency of antibiotic resistant bacteria
72 remains a big challenge also with the use of LbL assembly method. As an alternative, heavy metals,
73 such as iron, silver, copper, have been considered as promising PEs for multilayer assembly (17, 18).
74 However, their high loading has been shown to cause tissue toxicity and impaired wound healing
75 (19) and bacteria may develop a resistance to metal-based nanoparticles as reported for the silver
76 (20). Moreover, the incorporation of antibacterial peptides and enzymes has also emerged as

77 interesting approach for SSTIs (8), but their lack of stability during the LbL preparation has limited
78 their application (20).

79 In the last decade, the antimicrobial activity of different natural compounds has been reported in the
80 literature. As example, chitosan is a well-known biomaterial, obtained from the deacetylation of
81 chitin, produced from the exoskeleton of arthropods, that possesses hemostatic, antioxidant,
82 antitumoral and bactericidal behaviour (21). Furthermore, oregano, a worldwide used culinary herb,
83 showed antimicrobial and antioxidant properties due to the presence of thymol and flavonoids
84 respectively (22). An alternative natural-based agent, the honey, was proposed in this work in the
85 virtue of its ancient antibacterial properties. Honey has been used to treat infected wounds by
86 indigenous cultures around the globe before bacteria were discovered to be the cause of infections
87 (23). Although some honey varieties have demonstrated to have beneficial effects into infected sites,
88 most modern research has focused on a particular type produced in New Zealand from the nectar of
89 the *Leptospermum Scoparium* shrub, called Manuka honey (MH) (24). This honey contains the
90 constituents of other honey varieties, but its unique component, methylglyoxal, acts as an additional
91 antibacterial agent (25).

92 The increasing prevalence of data supporting honey's effectiveness as a natural broad-band
93 antibacterial agent has encouraged researchers in exploring MH as a wound treatment (26) or
94 incorporated in tissue-engineered hydrogels (27), demonstrating that MH could significantly reduce
95 the rate of infections on biomaterials, promote fibroblast migration and collagen deposition. In
96 addition, MH could enhance tissue-material integration/regeneration and accelerate healing of the
97 surrounding site (24). However, the undesirable cytotoxic effects of high concentrations of honey and
98 its uncontrolled release over time represent two of the greatest hurdles in the development of honey-
99 containing tissue-like substitutes (28). The LbL-assembly approach allows the incorporation of MH
100 with a subsequent and more efficient controlled release of honey from the nano-layers. This strategy
101 offers solutions to the current warning about the potential toxic effects of high honey concentration
102 on myofibroblasts and local mesenchymal-stem cells (29). Moreover, the main advantage of this
103 approach is the relatively small amount of honey loaded to achieve a therapeutic outcome, preventing
104 both bacteria resistance and drug-related systemic side effects.

105 In this work nano-structured honey-based coatings were deposited on biomimetic electrospun poly(ϵ -
106 caprolactone) meshes via LbL technique, to obtain discrete nanoscale layers to incorporate and to
107 control the MH release with minimal interaction with the biomaterial substrate. After the LbL
108 optimisation for achieving appropriate MH release kinetics, the nano-coating was characterised by
109 morphological and physico-chemical analyses to evaluate the multi-layered deposition, while by
110 biological and antibacterial behaviour to study the MH efficiency.

111 **2 Materials and methods**

112 **2.1 Materials**

113 Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL; Mw =82 kDa), poly(sodium4-styrenesulfonate) (PSS; Mw =70 kDa),
114 1,6-hexanediamine (ED), chloroform ($\geq 99.9\%$), formic acid ($\geq 95\%$) and sodium acetate buffer
115 solution were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, UK. Poly(allylamine hydrochloride) (PAH) was
116 supplied from Alfa Aesar, UK, while Medical grade Manuka honey (400 mg/kg of MGO) was
117 purchased from ManukaGuard®, US. Ultrapure water was obtained by a Milli-Q® Integral system
118 (Merck, Italy). All materials and chemicals were used without further purification.

119 **2.2 Electrospun membranes preparation**

120 PCL membranes were fabricated using an electrospinning system (Linari Engineering Srl, Italy).
121 Process and solution parameters were optimized to fabricate defect-free nanofibers with dimensions
122 in the hundreds of nanometers scale. Briefly, PCL pellets were solubilized using a chloroform and
123 formic acid solution (70/30 v/v) to obtain a 12% w/v concentration of the PCL solution. For each
124 membrane, 0.6 g of PCL were solubilized in 3.5 ml of chloroform for 1 hour under stirring and, then,
125 1.5 ml of formic acid were added and mixed for 20 minutes. The spinning process was performed at
126 room temperature and the spinning parameters were set as voltage of 20 kV, syringe flow rate of 1.5
127 ml/h, and nozzle-collector distance 20 cm.

128 2.3 Electrospun membranes functionalisation

129 PCL electrospun membranes (size 10×10 cm and thickness ≈200 μm) were aminolyzed by dipping
130 into ED solution (0.06 g/mL) for 10 min at 20 °C, in order to graft -NH₂- to get a positive charge on
131 the surface, and then abundantly washed in deionised water and left drying for 24 h. PSS (5 mg/ml),
132 PAH (5 mg/ml) and MH (15, 30, 60 and 120 mg/ml) solutions were prepared by dissolving the
133 polyelectrolytes in sodium acetate buffer solution (pH 5.3-5.5). The ζ-potentials of these solutions
134 was measured by laser Doppler electrophoresis (Zetasizer Nano, Malvern instrument, US). For the
135 LbL assembly, aminolysed membranes were dipped first into the polyanionic solutions (Manuka
136 Honey) for 15 min, followed by a washing step in sodium acetate buffer solution for 5 min to remove
137 any unbound PE material. The membranes were then soaked in the polycationic solution (PAH) for
138 15 min followed by a washing step using the same conditions described before. This dipping process
139 was repeated for eight cycles for creating 16 nanolayers. The samples were left to dry overnight,
140 coded as MH_1.5, MH_3, MH_6 and MH_12 the membranes functionalised by using different
141 concentration of Manuka Honey (1.5, 3, 6 and 12% w/v respectively) in sodium acetate buffer
142 solution (pH 5.3-5.5), while the membrane coated with PSS and PAH as PSS/PAH (used as control).

143 2.4 Physico-chemical characterisation

144 Quartz Crystal Microbalance Analyses (QCM-D) were performed with a QSense Explorer device
145 equipped with an open module (Q-Sense, Sweden). Changes in frequency (Δf) and energy dissipation
146 factor (ΔD) were monitored at its fundamental resonance frequency (5 MHz) and odd overtones (3, 5,
147 7, 9, 11, 13). Gold coated sensors (QSX301, Q-Sense, Sweden) were used and cleaned following
148 manufacture's instruction prior to use. Immediately after cleaning, a gold-coated sensor was placed in
149 the open module and 400 μl of ED solution were gently poured on the sensor surface using a
150 micropipette. After 10 minutes the ED solution was removed and 400 μl of sodium acetate buffer
151 solution were poured to remove non-adhered molecules. Then, the LbL process was reproduced by
152 alternating MH and PAH solutions to obtain 8-bilayers, following the same procedure described
153 before.

154 Morphological analysis of the samples before and after LbL dip assembly was performed by SEM
155 (Philips XL30-ESEM). Specimens were priority sputtered with a thin layer of gold (~10 nm, sputter
156 time 40 s at 40 mA). All the images were taken at 20 kV and working distance of 10 mm.

157 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) characterisation was performed with a Bruker Icon AFM with
158 TESP-V2 probes in Tapping Mode at 320 kHz frequency. The fibres were bonded to a metal stub
159 using two part-epoxy, and the loose fibres above the surface were manually removed to allow probe
160 access to the well-bonded fibres beneath.

161 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed with Theta Probe (Thermo Scientific, UK)
162 equipped with a microfocused AlKα X-ray source (1486.6 eV), operated with a 400 μm spot size

163 (100 W power). Process parameters were: 200 eV pass energy, 1 eV step size of and of 50 ms dwell
164 time in not angle-resolved lens mode. Moreover, high resolution spectra were acquired with 40eV
165 pass energy, 0.1 eV step size and 200 ms as dwell time. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra
166 were acquired in a wavenumber range of 4000–550 cm^{-1} using Spectrum Two PE instrument
167 equipped with a horizontal attenuated total reflectance (ATR) crystal (ZnSe) (PerkinElmer Inc, US; 4
168 cm^{-1} resolution and 32 scans).

169 The amount of Manuka Honey released from the membranes was analysed by in vitro tests after
170 immersion of 1x1 cm membranes in 1ml of Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS, Sigma-Aldrich, UK)
171 solution at 37 °C for different time points (up to 4weeks). The released solution of the soaked
172 membranes was assayed for glucose (Glucose Assay Kit, Sigma-Aldrich, UK) as proposed by Hixon
173 (30).

174 2.5 Cell tests

175 Membranes with a diameter of 15 cm were treated with Sudan Black (SB, Sigma-Aldrich, UK) to
176 avoid the auto-fluorescence of the electrospun membranes: 0.3% (w/v) SB solution was prepared in
177 70% ethanol and the membranes were immersed in this solution for 15min, and, then, rinsed 3 times
178 in PBS solution and sterilised under UV light for 30 min (31).

179 Different cell lines were used to test the membranes cytocompatibility. Human hTERT immortalized
180 fibroblast from non-malignant myoma (T-HESCs, ATCC, CRL-4003™) were cultured from frozen
181 stock in a 1:1 mixture of Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) and Ham's F-12 medium
182 with 3.1 g/L glucose and 1 mM sodium pyruvate and without phenol red (Sigma-Aldrich, UK)
183 supplemented with 1.5 g/L sodium bicarbonate, 1%ITS+ Premix (Corning, UK), 500 ng/mL
184 puromycin, 10% charcoal/dextran treated fetal bovine serum (HyClone, US). Healthy skin human
185 fibroblasts, kindly donated by Ana Tiganescu at Saint James's Teaching Hospital in Leeds (isolated
186 from skin biopsies samples obtained from the Tissue Bank repository) were cultured in 1:1 mixture
187 of DMEM with high glucose, Glutamax and 10% fetal bovine serum. Finally, primary human
188 umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) were isolated from umbilical cord obtained from de-
189 identified term placenta collected from patients who underwent elective caesarean section between
190 37 and 39 weeks of gestation. After isolation, 95% purity of endothelial cells was observed, validated
191 morphologically and by immunofluorescent staining for CD31 (DAKO, US) before seeding on the
192 membranes. Cells were cultured in EBM-2 medium supplemented with EGM-2 Single Quot growth
193 factors (Lonza, US). All the cell lines were maintained at 37°C in a saturated humidity atmosphere
194 containing 5% CO_2 , and they were sub-cultured before reaching 60–70% confluence (approximately
195 every 2 days) up to passage 5. All the cells were passaged and seeded on the different meshes at
196 density of 5,000 cells/ cm^2 (~20,000 cell/well in a 12 well plate).

197 LIVE/DEAD staining (ReadyProbes® Cell Viability Imaging Kit, Molecular probes) was used
198 following manufacturer protocols to determine the viability of cells and to check proliferation of cells
199 exposed for 8 days to medium conditioned with Manuka Honey (1.3% v/v and 8.3% v/v) and on the
200 different substrates after 8 days in culture.

201 2.6 Bacterial tests

202 The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of Manuka honey to Gram-positive *S. aureus* (ATCC
203 25923), *S. epidermidis* (ATCC 12228) and Gram-negative *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) and *P. aeruginosa*
204 (ATCC 10145) was determined according to Wiegand et al. (32). Manuka honey was tested at
205 concentrations ranging from 3.125 to 500 mg/ml. Bacterial suspensions at the concentration of 5×10^5

206 Colony Forming Units (CFU)/ml were inoculated into Mueller Hinton Broth in absence (control) or
207 in presence of the different concentrations of honey and the multi-well plates incubated at 37°C for
208 16-20 h. MIC was identified as the lowest concentration of honey that prevents visible growth of the
209 tested strains as observed with the unaided eye. Assays were conducted in triplicate and repeated
210 twice.

211 The antimicrobial effectiveness of LbL-functionalized electrospun membranes was assessed using 3-
212 [4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT)-based colorimetric assay (33).
213 Bacterial suspensions at a concentration of 5×10^5 CFU/ml were prepared in Tryptic Soy Broth
214 (TSB). Afterwards, 1 ml of each of these suspensions was used to dip all the membranes, previously
215 sterilized by 30 minutes UV treatment, in 5ml tubes. Samples were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours at
216 120 rpm. At the end of the incubation time, bacteria were harvested by centrifugation at 12000rpm
217 for 10 minutes and incubated for 30 minutes in 1ml of MTT working solution containing 0.03 g of
218 MTT (Sigma-Aldrich, Italy) in 9.85ml of PBS supplemented with 50 μ l of a 20% glucose solution
219 and 100 μ l of a 1 mM menadione solution. Bacteria were then harvested by centrifugation at 12000
220 rpm for 10 minutes and resuspended in 1 ml of DMSO:glycine 0.1 M pH 10.2 (7:1) buffer. Finally,
221 absorbance of each sample was measured by spectrophotometric reading at 570 nm wavelength. The
222 percentage of inhibition of functionalized fibers, compared to PCL fibers (controls), was determined
223 as $[1 - (\text{Abstreat}/\text{Absctrl})] \times 100$, where Abstreat indicates optical density of functionalized samples
224 and Absctrl corresponds to the optical density of controls.

225 2.7 Statistical analysis

226 All the experiments were performed at least in triplicate. Results were expressed as a mean \pm
227 standard deviation and statistical significance was calculated using analysis of variance (ANOVA).
228 The comparison between two means was analysed using Tukey's test with statistical significance
229 level set at * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ and *** $p < 0.001$.

230 3 Results

231 Electrophoresis measurements were performed, showing that MH-based solutions ranging from 1.5%
232 to 12% w/v were negatively charged with ζ -potentials from -12.6 to -22.4 mV, while PAH solution
233 was positively charged with a ζ -potential of +14.5 mV. As a control, negatively charge PSS solution
234 was selected in order to favour complexation due to its strong interaction with PAH. This had a ζ -
235 potential of -18.8 mV. Furthermore, the evaluation of the electrostatic interaction between MH in
236 different concentration and PAH was investigated by QCM-D measurements, in order to confirm the
237 formation of the multilayered structures (34).

238 As shown in **Figure 1**, the presence of ED solution caused a shift in both frequency and dissipation
239 when NH₂ groups interacted with the Au surface of the sensor. The subsequent cleaning step
240 partially removed the layer as confirmed by the increase of Δf values (Δf value after cleaning step \approx -
241 300 Hz) at around 620 seconds. Then, MH and PAH polyelectrolyte solutions were alternatively
242 flowed across the positively-charged functionalised Au-crystal for 15 minutes in order to simulate the
243 LbL dipping conditions of electrospun membranes. The addition of polyelectrolytes molecules on the
244 crystal surface was confirmed by a cumulative step-wise response of Δf and ΔD , where the black
245 stars indicated the shift caused by the Manuka Honey-based solutions. The subsequent cleaning step
246 removed the majority of both polyelectrolytes in the first bi-layers. Starting from the third bi-layer,
247 the deposition of MH was more evident, particularly for MH₆ and MH₁₂, while for MH₃ a
248 significant Δf was observed with the formation of the fourth bi-layer. Furthermore, the ΔD trend

249 confirmed the formation of a thicker layer on the top of the Au-crystal as the dissipation factor
250 increased with time.

251 The surface morphology of the multilayered coating after LbL assembly was analysed by Scanning
252 Electron Microscopy (SEM) (**Figure 2(A)**). The electrospun membranes presented an average fibres
253 diameter of $0.75 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{m}$ and an intrinsic micro-porosity. After LbL functionalisation, the
254 membranes coated with MH and PAH appeared smooth and uniform, leading to an increase in the
255 fiber-diameter, which in turn resulted proportional to the number of bi-layers used. The control
256 PSS/PAH-coated membranes showed a formation of irregular shaped protuberances, and a
257 consequently higher surface roughness and fiber diameter in comparison to the bare substrate.
258 Furthermore, AFM analysis (**Figure 2(B)**) confirmed the successful functionalisation of the
259 membranes, and in addition it was possible to visualise the extent of the MH coating in detail using
260 the tapping mode phase contrast signal. The clean PCL fibres were smooth to a sub-nm level, but in
261 phase contrast showed striations of 13.5 nm periodicity around the circumference of the fibre
262 (alternative dark and light stripes of approximately 7 nm width) (**Figure 3**).

263 As with SEM, the PSS/PAH showed a thick, irregular and continuous coating. MH 1.5 to 12 w/v %
264 revealed a clear progression of MH coverage. At 1.5% w/v MH the coating (bright gold vs the darker
265 brown PCL in **Figure 2(B)** and **3**) forms a quite sparse network across the fibre surface. At 3% MH
266 the strands of this network have thickened and begin to enclose regions of clean PCL. At 6% MH the
267 network has fused into an almost continuous coating with a small number of patches of PCL fibre
268 visible. These remaining patches have almost entirely gone at 12% MH, and a continuous coating has
269 formed.

270 The surface coverage of MH visible in the high resolution AFM phase images was analysed by
271 thresholding to discriminate the coating (**Figure 3**) and analysing in ImageJ (NIH) using the
272 histogram function. The resultant concentration vs coverage response (**Figure 4(B)**) is reminiscent of
273 an absorption isotherm, and a Langmuir-Freundlich isotherm (35) (allowing for heterogenous and
274 multi-layer films) was used to fit the film growth, giving an absorption rate constant $k = 6.35 \times 10^{-3}$
275 L/g.

276 Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR-ATR) and X-ray photoelectron (XPS) were performed to analyse the
277 surface membranes composition before and after LbL assembly. Particularly, the infrared spectra
278 (**Figure 5**) revealed the presence of the characteristic chemical bands of the polyelectrolytes used for
279 coating the PCL electrospun membranes. For the poly(allylamine hydrochloride) the following
280 chemical bands were observed: $\nu\text{N-H}$ stretching (3360 cm^{-1}); alkyl $\nu\text{C-H}$ stretching (2920 cm^{-1}); N-H
281 symmetric and asymmetric scissoring vibrations (1490 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} respectively), and $\nu\text{N-H}$
282 asymmetric stretching (1330 cm^{-1}) (9); while the presence of the honey was characterised by different
283 absorption zones dominated by two water bands at $3300\text{-}3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH stretch) and 1641 cm^{-1} (OH
284 deformation). The band from about $1500\text{-}750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was related to the most sensitive absorption
285 region of the honey's major components; particularly the most suitable region to quantify honey
286 sugar (59–75%) and organic acids. The small peak at 1110 cm^{-1} corresponded to stretching of the C–
287 O band of the C–O–C linkage and the peak at around 1690 cm^{-1} corresponded to C=O stretching
288 (36). However, all the other honey distinctive peaks were overlapped with the other components of
289 PCL and PAH.

290 **Figure 6** shows the XPS survey spectra before and after LbL assembly functionalisation. The
291 surveys showed N1s peak at 399.5 eV, demonstrating PAH was successfully introduced, while C1s at
292 285 eV and O1s at 630 eV peaks were characteristics of both PAH and Manuka honey. Moreover the
293 presence of Na1s at 1070 eV and Cl2p at 200 eV was due to the addition of NaCl in the
294 polyelectrolyte solution for maintaining a stable charge (37). The high resolution spectra for C1s
295 along with the curve fit showed three peaks attributed to the different Carbon oxidation states: (1)
296 284.7–285.0, (2) 286.8–287.0, and (3) 288.5–289 eV, corresponding to $-\text{C-H}$ or $-\text{C-C-}$ bonds, to

297 –C–O– bond, and to –C=O groups respectively. It was observed that these components content varied
298 significantly with the formation of the layers. The concentration of C=O decreased with the
299 formation of the nanocoating, because it was characteristic of PCL chemical structure. On the other
300 hand, the component corresponding to C–N bonds increased suggesting the polyelectrolytes coating.
301 Finally the high resolution spectra for N1s revealed the presence of PAH layers in all the coated
302 electrospun membranes (no signal present in bare PCL membrane).

303 The release of glucose was measured over 14 days (**Figure 7**). The LbL-functionalised membranes
304 showed three different stages in the release profile as shown for all the samples, where, as expected,
305 the membrane functionalised with the higher MH content showed the highest glucose released. A
306 burst release was observed with approximately the 10-12% of MH delivered during the initial 24
307 hours of incubation ($392.6 \pm 47.5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ for MH_12), followed by a controlled and linear MH release
308 up to 14 days ($1.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg/ml}$ for MH_12). At 28 days no significant change in MH release was
309 noticed for all the samples, probably due to the nanocoating degradation that implied a zero-order
310 release.

311 When the effect of medium supplemented with MH was evaluated in respect to MH free medium, the
312 LIVE/DEAD staining showed 100% viable healthy fibroblasts in all the sample: after staining with
313 propidium iodide solution, no signal was detected using a standard TRITC/RFP (orange) filter set,
314 meaning that all the cells had an intact plasma membrane (**Figure 8**). A slower proliferation,
315 however, was observed in high concentrated samples, but not significant in comparison to the control
316 condition.

317 Then, three different cell types were seeded on all the functionalised electrospun meshes for 8 days.
318 Before seeding the cells, all the substrates were treated with Sudan Black (SB). This is a quenching
319 compound commonly used in lipid histochemistry in order to better visualize biological structure.
320 Using a concentration of 0.3% (w/v) SB in ethanol that was previously proven to be not toxic and to
321 successfully cancel background fluorescence of polymeric scaffolds (38), it was possible to image the
322 live and dead cells after 10 days in culture on most of the samples.

323 Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed only between proliferation on PSS/PAH and MH_6
324 and MH_12 coated fibers (as shown in **Figure 9(A)**). The proliferation of fibroblasts on PSS/PAH
325 sample was lower and statistically different compared to all the other samples. For immortalized
326 THESC, the proliferation was significantly decreased on PCL samples, while the concentration of
327 Manuka Honey did not significantly affect the viability. Significant higher proliferation was observed
328 on PSS/PAH fibers compared to MH_6 coated substrates. Honey coated fibers supported
329 proliferation of primary endothelial cells with no significant differences depending on the
330 concentration of honey. Proliferation was significantly lower on PSS/PAH and bare PCL samples
331 compared to the maximum value obtained on MH_1.5 and MH_3 coated fibers ($p < 0.05$).

332 Finally, the antibacterial activity of Manuka Honey against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative
333 species was evaluated by the broth microdilution method. The assay showed a Minimum Inhibitory
334 Concentration (MIC) at 200 mg/ml (13.6% v/v) for *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*, at 300 mg/ml
335 (20.4% v/v) for *E. coli* and at 500 mg/ml (34% v/v) for *P. aeruginosa*. The antibacterial activity of 2
336 mg of each LbL-functionalized electrospun membrane was quantified by means of the MTT assay.

337 **Figure 9(B)** shows the differences in the metabolic activity of cells co-incubated for 24h with the
338 different types of membranes. In comparison with neat PCL membranes, PSS/PAH samples showed
339 no antibacterial activity. On the other hand, the efficacy of Honey-LbL-functionalised electrospun
340 membranes depended on the content of Manuka Honey and on the tested strain. Honey-
341 functionalized membranes had no significant efficacy against the Gram-negative species *E. coli* and
342 *P. aeruginosa* (averagely from 1.1% to 11.1% inhibition). Increasing but negligible inhibitions were
343 observed against *S. aureus* for MH_1.5, MH_3 and MH_6 samples whereas a significant reduction of
344 27.2% was detected for MH_12 ($p < 0.001$). For *S. epidermidis*, significant inhibitory activities of
345 13.5% for MH_3, of 23.4% for MH_6 and of 34.3% for MH_12 were found ($p < 0.001$).

346 **4 Discussion**

347 Bacterial resistance to antimicrobial agents is an increasing health and economic problem (39). As an
348 alternative to antimicrobial drugs, the therapeutic use of ancient remedies has been reevaluated in
349 recent years. Honey is known for its therapeutic potential, including wound healing properties and
350 antimicrobial activity. Since ancient times, honey has been a traditional remedy of several human
351 diseases (40). The antibacterial properties of honey are strongly influenced by its high osmolarity,
352 acidity, content of hydrogen peroxide, and in the specific case of Manuka honey, also by
353 phytochemical components like methylglyoxal (MGO) and leptosperin (41). However, toxic cellular
354 effects of the honey-derived agents could potentially limit its clinical use. To date only a few papers
355 have shown the cytocompatibility of Manuka Honey-based structures for tissue engineering
356 applications, reporting the correlation of MH concentration with its toxicity to human cells. In this
357 work, we proposed: (1) Layer-by-Layer assembly as an effective surface functionalisation
358 technology, and (2) for the first time Manuka Honey as a polyelectrolyte within the LbL assembly
359 strategy in order to confer antibacterial properties and preserve the cytocompatibility of PCL
360 electrospun membranes. Among others, electrospinning technology offers the unique opportunity to
361 develop ECM-like substrates, with biomimetic features, able to enhance soft tissue regeneration. In
362 addition to this, as demonstrated recently by Gentile et al (9), LbL technology allows the
363 incorporation of a relatively small amount of loaded drug/biomolecules needed to achieve effective
364 concentrations for a localised and controlled delivery system without affecting the physico-chemical
365 properties of the substrate.

366 Therefore in order to consider MH as a novel polyelectrolyte, electrophoresis measurements were
367 performed and they showed that MH-based solutions were negatively charged and the MH trend was
368 in accordance with previous studies, where the ζ -potential was significantly influenced by the
369 concentration of different studied polysaccharides. Particularly, sodium alginate and k-carrageenan
370 solutions, considered as weak polyelectrolytes, showed that the increase of the polysaccharide
371 concentrations lead to more negative ζ -potential values (42). On the other hand, it was reported in
372 literature that strong polyelectrolytes, such as polyethyleneimine (PEI), were characterised by an
373 opposite trend, where an increase of the polymer concentration lead to lower ζ -potential values (43).
374 This indicates that MH acts as a partially-weak polyelectrolyte as the natural-based polyelectrolytes.

375 A confirmation of the MH potential within LbL functionalisation was provided by QCM-D
376 measurements, where MH and PAH demonstrated a stable electrostatic complexation with the
377 tendency of PAH to form a more rigid layer in comparison to MH, as the dissipation factor
378 underwent a more pronounced shift when MH layer was recorded (44).

379 Biomimetic fiber-based membranes were produced through electrospinning to mimic the nanofibrous
380 structure of the native ECM (45). Among other polymers, PCL was selected as former material
381 thanks to its well know biocompatibility and its stability during LbL processing without
382 compromising bulk material properties and structure morphology (46). For the optimal
383 functionalisation conditions of PCL-based electrospun membranes via LbL assembly, the process
384 parameters were set as follows: a total number of 16 nanolayers, dipping time into the PE solutions of
385 15 minutes, PAH molar concentration of 0.5 M, in accordance to a previous work reported by the
386 authors (12). In order to favour the absorption of the first polyelectrolyte, aminolysis treatment was
387 performed before the LbL assembly functionalisation in order to incorporate primary and secondary
388 NH₂ groups onto the substrate (47). The surface functionalisation did not influence the intrinsic
389 micro-porosity of the electrospun membranes, which is fundamental for cell penetration, nutrient
390 transport and waste removal (48), and to make them available biocues of the native ECM (45).

391 Particularly SEM showed for the control PSS/PAH-coated membranes a formation of irregular
392 shaped protuberances, and a consequently higher surface roughness and fiber diameter in comparison
393 to the bare substrate. This is typical of strong complexation between these two polyelectrolytes and
394 becomes more evident with an increasing the number of bi-layers, as demonstrated by several studies
395 (49, 50) . On the other hand, similarly to other natural polyelectrolytes, MH coating appeared smooth
396 and uniform, leading to an increase in the fiber-diameter, which in turn resulted proportional to the
397 number of bi-layers used (51, 52).

398 Although not quantitative, AFM tapping mode phase contrast signal can very clearly differentiate
399 different material properties, and our work the coating substance showed a reduced phase lag (lighter
400 in the images) compared with the PCL fibre (darker phase contrast). In phase contrast PCL fibres
401 showed typical striations (13.5 nm periodicity around the fibre circumference), that are the polymer
402 crystalline lamellae of the PCL layered between amorphous regions, as observed previously in 100%
403 PCL fibres with a spacing of 14.8 ± 2.9 nm (53), a value which increased upon addition of another
404 polymer to the fibre composition. In most partially crystalline polymers these lamellae typically lie in
405 the range 10-20 nm. They are more visible in the high resolution AFM phase contrast images of the
406 fibres (for PCL and MH_1.5). Furthermore, AFM indicated that the resultant concentration vs
407 coverage response was indicative of an absorption isotherm, where the progressive coverage with
408 concentration indicates that absorption of the partially strong polyelectrolyte to this heterogenous and
409 porous surface follows a typical surface absorption mechanism, as well as being subject to LbL
410 growth once the initial absorption site have taken hold. During the LbL process at a given
411 concentration these sites will gradually thicken and spread out filling in the remaining uncoated
412 regions (for a cartoon schematic of this mechanism (see **Figure 10**).

413 In this work we reported a lower MH-loaded content, comparing with other papers reported in
414 literature, with a more controlled release in the longer period. Hixon et al. reported a release of 0.5
415 mg/ml of MH for the first 24 hours, followed by a slight decrease at 4 days and a sustained break
416 down after 7 days (30). In our work, we demonstrated that LbL assembly can be an effective
417 methodology for having a controlled release of the natural antibacterial agent within 2 weeks that
418 represent the period in which most implant-associated infections are initiated (54).

419 Finally, biological tests demonstrated that MH coating supported proliferation of different cell types
420 (fibroblasts and endothelial cells) without compromising the biocompatibility of the meshes, while the
421 antibacterial ones showed that the antimicrobial MH activity was dependent on the concentration used
422 and the bacteria strain tested. In accordance with our observation, Bucekova et al. (55) demonstrated
423 that medical-grade Manuka honey was more effective against Gram-positive than Gram-negative
424 bacteria. Similar results were shown by Tan et al. (56) with MIC₉₅ values of 12.5% (v/v) and 20% (v/v)
425 for *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively.

426 Furthermore, *E. coli* inhibition was demonstrated by means of the agar diffusion assay for PCL
427 scaffolds containing 10% and 20% of MH by Minden-Birkenmaier et al. (19). Yang et al. reported
428 bacterial inhibition rates of different MH/silk fibroin fibrous (SF) matrices (57). In particular, for MH
429 (10%)/SF, an inhibitory effect ranging from 5% to 10% was detected against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P.*
430 *aeruginosa* and MRSA strains. The observed dependence to the bacterial strain might be identified, at
431 first, in the structural differences of their cell walls. In comparison to Gram-negative strains, in fact,
432 Gram-positives do not have an outer membrane that offers protection to the peptidoglycan layer from
433 lysozyme and other antimicrobial agents, making them easier to penetrate and damage (58) . Secondly,
434 the different grade of susceptibility of bacterial strains might be also due to the different mechanisms
435 of action involved in MH's antibacterial activity (59). For example, for *S. aureus* it was observed that

436 MH interferes with the regular cell division process (52). Conversely, for *P. aeruginosa* it was observed
437 that inhibitory concentrations cause the loss of cellular integrity, extensive cell lysis and death (60).

438 Overall, the advantages of the nano-functionalisation strategy described here are marked: (1) to allow
439 the manufacturing of biomimetic systems with expectable functional properties without
440 compromising the physico-chemical properties of the electrospun membranes; (2) in vitro release
441 demonstrated that the MH-loaded meshes were capable of effectively delivering MH in a controlled
442 way within two-three weeks of incubation; and (3) in vitro tests confirmed the cytocompatibility of
443 all the proposed MH-based systems while the antibacterial ones showed that the antimicrobial MH
444 activity was dependent on the concentration used and the bacteria strain tested. This study has
445 therefore demonstrated that the combination of naturally-derived antibacterial agent with LbL
446 technique may be applied to the manufacture of medical devices with advanced functionality.

447 **Conflict of Interest**

448 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
449 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

450 **Author Contributions**

451 E.M., P.G. conceived the study. E.M., L.F., S.D., and P.G. designed the experiments, E.M. and P.G.
452 performed the LbL functionalisation; C.T.T. produced the membranes and performed the QCM; S.D.
453 performed the AFM; E.M. performed the SEM; V.P. performed the *in vitro* cell tests; C.C. and L.F.
454 performed the bacterial tests; all the authors analysed and interpreted the data and prepared the
455 manuscript.

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461

462 **Data Availability Statement**

463 Datasets are available on request: the raw data supporting the conclusions of this manuscript will be
464 made available by the authors, without undue reservation, to any qualified researcher.

465 **Figure Captions**

466 **Figure 1.** Plot of the fifth overtone of Δf (A) and ΔD (B) versus time. Stars indicate events associated
467 to the dipping step in Manuka Honey solution.

468 **Figure 2.** (A) SEM and (B) AFM images of the electrospun membranes before and after LbL assembly
469 functionalisation.

470 **Figure 3.** MH adsorption analysis – conversion to thresholded images prior to image analysis in
471 ImageJ.

472 **Figure 4.** (A) High resolution AFM phase contrast images. (B) Analysis of MH coating coverage from
473 high resolution AFM images.

474 **Figure 5.** FTIR-ATR spectra of the electrospun membranes before and after LbL assembly
475 functionalisation.

476 **Figure 6.** XPS survey spectra and high resolution C1s spectra of the electrospun membranes before
477 and after LbL assembly functionalisation.

478 **Figure 7.** Glucose assay for honey detection.

479 **Figure 8.** Proliferation of fibroblasts in medium supplemented with Manuka honey at different
480 concentrations. Blue nuclei staining (NucBlue® Live reagent) of cells cultured in (a) DMEM (control),
481 (b) DMEM supplemented with Honey 1.3 % v/v, (c) DMEM supplemented with Honey 8.3 % v/v was
482 detected using a standard DAPI filter. All the picture are recorded with magnification 4x, scale bar 100
483 mm.

484 **Figure 9.** (A) Cell viability of Dermal fibroblasts (i), immortalized THESC (ii) and HUVECs (iii) on
485 PCL, PSS/PAH, Honey1.5%, 3%, 6%, 12%. * mark significantly different samples. (B) Metabolic
486 activity measured by MTT assay of 4 different strains incubated for 24h with nano-functionalised
487 membranes.

488 **Figure 10.** Schematic cartoon of the LbL mechanism.

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